

ACQUISITION OF EQUIPMENT AND CAREER SUCCESS AMONG GRADUATE FASHION DESIGN PRACTITIONERS IN OYO STATE

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Abstract

This study investigated acquisition of equipment and career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State. Literature shows that many graduate fashion designers are not achieving success and satisfaction in their career. The descriptive survey research design was employed. The population comprised all graduate fashion design practitioners (1,445) in Lagelu, Kajola, and Ibadan North LGAs out of which 821 were sampled using Yamane sampling technique. Questionnaire titled – “Acquisition of Equipment and Career Success Questionnaire (AECSQ) ($\alpha = .762$)” was used to collect data. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Results showed moderate level of career success in areas of acquisition of assets ($\bar{x} = 2.530$), family needs attainment ($\bar{x} = 2.530$), and career satisfaction ($\bar{x} = 2.533$) and low level in area of employment generation ($\bar{x} = 2.409$). Results showed rare availability of acquisition of equipment ($\bar{x} = 2.349$) for fashion design practice. Hypothesis revealed significant relationship between availability of acquisition of equipment ($r = .138$; $P < 0.05$) and career success. It was concluded that rare availability of acquisition of equipment is responsible for graduate fashion design practitioners’ moderate level of career success in areas of acquisition of assets, family needs attainment, and career satisfaction and low level in area of employment generation. It was recommended amongst others that the graduate fashion design practitioners should solicit for funds to acquire more equipment thus making them available for use to boost their career success.

Keywords: Acquisition of Equipment, Career success, Fashion Design Practice

Introduction

Fashion design practice is a career associated with designing and making of cloths and dresses to cover the human body for protection and beautification (Nzei,2022). Fashion design practice is one major entrepreneurial venture that both male and female graduates in Nigeria including Oyo state have delved into for several reasons such as interests, passion, and most especially the inability to get jobs (unemployment) in public and private sectors after graduation (Aduwa, 2020). As a result of these reasons, several graduates have decided to build a career in various entrepreneurial ventures such as fashion design practice with the sole aim of achieving career success.

Career success which could be objective (extrinsic) or subjective (intrinsic) is the favourable material and psychological results that a graduate fashion design practitioner has achieved from fashion design practice (Das & Chandrasekaran, 2024). Objective perspective on career success takes the tangible facets of graduate fashion design practitioner's career into account, such as ability to acquire assets (lands, houses, machines, and etcetera), generate employment for others, and meet family needs with ease (Nexhip et al., 2023). However, intrinsic or subjective career success is a graduate fashion design practitioner's internal satisfaction with his or her work or career (Farla et al., 2021).

Many graduate fashion design practitioners ventured into fashion design career with the hope of attaining career success. However, this has not been the case as some graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State are yet to attain intrinsic and/or extrinsic career success. Literature is replete with evidence of low career success among some graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State (Adegbenle, 2021; Adeleke & Ojewale, 2023; Ashamu & Olateju, 2023; Ayodele, 2021; Obialo & Adelore, 2023; Oghenovo, 2022; Osuntayo, 2017). Several reasons for the cause of low career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State have been proffered. Most of them include - entrepreneurial training, empowerment, environmental factors, and apprenticeship training (Adeleke & Ojewale, 2023; Ashamu & Olateju, 2023; Ayodele, 2021; Osuntayo, 2017). However, salient factor such as acquisition of equipment as determinant of career success of graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State has not been given adequate attention in literature.

In the context of this study, acquisition of equipment refers to the ability of graduate fashion design practitioners to acquire assets in the form of equipment or materials for their fashion design practice in Oyo State. These equipments include all operational work tools, objects or machines such as sewing machines (computerized machines, industrial sewing machines), weaving or serger machines, quilting machines, stoning machines, embroidery machines and etcetera used by graduate fashion design practitioners to directly or indirectly produce outfits in Oyo State (Nasrullah et al., 2020). Thus, the level at which these equipments are acquired and made available for use could determine how much success a graduate fashion design practitioners is able to attain in his or her fashion design career.

A report showed a positive link between resource availability and career success of entrepreneurs in Nigeria (Salisu et al., 2022). In a study, sewing machines such as quilting

machine, computerized machine and serger machine were found to provide opportunities for easier sewing, produce attractive stitches on fabrics and reduce unemployment among youths through creation of innovative styles and modern trends in fashion designs in Rivers State (Azunwena et al., 2018). Studies are however lacking on acquisition of equipment and career success of graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State. This study thus sought to find out if acquisition of equipment influences the level of extrinsic and intrinsic career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State.

Statement of the Problem

As a result of the huge scarcity of employment opportunities, many graduates in Oyo State delved into various kinds of entrepreneurial enterprises such as fashion design practice. However, many of them are yet to attain career success in the venture. Studies show low career success among many graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State (Adegbenle, 2021; Adeleke & Ojewale, 2023; Ashamu & Olateju, 2023; Ayodele, 2021; Obialo & Adelore, 2023; Oghenovo, 2022; Osuntayo, 2017). Some of the graduate fashion design practitioners do not earn enough income to meet their needs and that of their family. Some of them are still not able to purchase lands, houses, cars, and various assets despite being in the fashion industry for quite some time. Some are still unable to expand their business, employ others and be satisfied despite being in the fashion design business for a long period of time ((Adegbenle, 2021; Adeleke & Ojewale, 2023; Ashamu & Olateju, 2023; Ayodele, 2021; Obialo & Adelore, 2023; Oghenovo, 2022; Osuntayo, 2017). This study thus sought to investigate whether a crucial factor like acquisition of equipment may be influencing career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State.

Research Questions

This study attempted to find answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of career success (acquisition of assets, employment generation, family needs attainment and career satisfaction) among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State?
2. What is the availability level of acquired equipment for use among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There will be no significant relationship between availability level of acquired equipment for use and career success (acquisition of assets, employment generation, family needs attainment and career satisfaction) among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State

Literature Review

Theoretical Review

This study was hinged on the Resource Based Theory (RBT). Resource Based Theory (RBT) shows that a business performance or profitability or career success is directly related to the resources owned and controlled by the firm or business or enterprise (Penrose, 1959). The theory postulates that a business enterprise is dependent on how a firm controls its equipments acquired and made available. The theory also posits that the services delivered to clients by an organisation are a function of the way material resources are available and used. The central premise of RBT is that firms or businesses compete on the basis of the equipment at their disposal. The theory proposes that business organisations gain a competitive advantage by deploying a valuable bundle of resources and capabilities that are inelastic in supply. Consequently, the emphasis of the theory is on acquisition of material resources from which a business can gain competitive advantage and the combination of such heterogeneous resources in a manner that guarantees greater performance, profitability, and success. However, the emphasis here is that an organisation can only build a competitive and profitable enterprise if the right material resources are available and properly utilized (Murimi et al., 2019; Penrose, 1959).

Methodology

This research employed the descriptive survey research design. The target population comprised all male and female graduate fashion design practitioners (1,445) in three popular and highly busy local government areas (Lagelu, Kajola and Ibadan North) across the three senatorial districts in Oyo State. The Taro Yamane sample size determination formula was used to arrive at a sample size of eight hundred and twenty-one (821) graduate fashion design practitioners for the study. The formula is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where **n** is the needed sample size,

N is the population size, and

e is the level of precision.

A researcher-constructed questionnaire titled: “Acquisition of Equipment and Career Success Questionnaire (AECSQ) was used to collect data. The questionnaire was validated using content and face validity and subjected to Cronbach’s alpha for estimation of its internal consistency (stability). Value of .762 was obtained which meant that the questionnaire is stable (that is, reliable). The instrument was made into several copies and administered to the sample number (836) of graduate fashion design practitioners. Demographic variables of graduate fashion design practitioners were analysed using frequency and percentage. Research questions were answered using frequency counts, percentages, mean, and standard deviation while inferential statistics such as Pearson product moment correlation was used to analyse the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Demographic Data Analysis

Table 1: Demographic Data of Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n= 821)

Demographic Variables	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	321	39.1
Female	500	60.9
Age (Years)		
20 and below	100	12.2
21-30	298	36.3
31-40	302	36.8
41-50	105	12.8
51 and above	16	1.9
Highest Academic Qualification		
NCE	110	13.4
OND	201	24.5
HND	224	27.3
Bachelor’s Degree	236	28.7
Master’s Degree	50	6.1
Years of Fashion Design Practice		
1-5	258	31.4
6-10	306	37.3
11-15	201	24.5
16 and above	56	6.8

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 1 showed that 321 respondents in the study representing 39.1% are male graduate fashion design practitioners while 500 respondents representing 60.9% are females. Majority of the respondents, 302 (36.8%) are within 31-40 years of age, 236 (28.7%) have Bachelor’s degree, and 306 (37.3%) have 6-10 years of experience. This result implies that majority among

the graduate fashion design practitioners are university graduates and have above 5 years of experience in fashion design practice which is commendable.

Answer to Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the level of career success (acquisition of assets, employment generation, family needs attainment and career satisfaction) among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State?

Table 2: Level of Acquisition of Assets among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	I have acquired more sewing machines including industrial, embroidery and stoning machines through my fashion practice	201 (24.5%)	358 (43.6%)	147 (17.9%)	115 (14.0%)	2.786	.713
2.	I have acquired more shops through fashion practice	120 (14.6%)	257 (31.3%)	200 (24.4%)	244 (29.7%)	2.308	.998
3.	I have landed properties through fashion design practice	110 (13.4%)	201 (24.5%)	308 (37.5%)	202 (24.6%)	2.267	1.010
4.	I have bought at least a car through fashion practice	205 (25.0%)	315 (38.4%)	198 (24.1%)	103 (12.5%)	2.758	.716
Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.530 (.859);		Decision = Moderate Level					

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Key: High Level (HL) = 4, Moderate Level (ML) = 3, Low Level (LL) = 2, Very Low Level (VLL) = 1; Std. Dev. = Standard Deviation; **Threshold Mean:** 1.000-1.750 = Very Low Level; 1.751-2.500 = Low Level; 2.501-3.250 = Moderate Level and 3.251 to 4.000 = High Level

Table 2 showed the level of career success in area of acquisition of assets among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The rating scale of Very Low Level (1) to High Level (4) was used. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.530$) clearly indicates that generally, the level of acquisition of assets among the graduate fashion design practitioners is at a moderate level (slightly above low level).

Table 3: Level of Employment Generation among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std.Dev.
1.	My fashion design practice have provided new opportunities for paid employment	199 (24.2%)	210 (25.6%)	214 (26.1%)	198 (24.1%)	2.499	.983
2.	I have workers on my payroll in my fashion enterprise	153 (18.6%)	269 (32.8%)	201 (24.5%)	198 (24.1%)	2.459	.987
3.	I pay my workers very well in my fashion design enterprise	141 (17.2%)	249 (30.3%)	175 (21.3%)	256 (31.2%)	2.335	1.001
4.	I pay my workers regularly as at when due in my fashion design enterprise	138 (16.8%)	239 (29.1%)	209 (25.5%)	235 (28.6%)	2.341	.995
Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.409 (.992); Decision = Low Level							

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 3 showed the level of career success in area of employment generation among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.409$) clearly indicates that generally, the level of employment generation among the graduate fashion design practitioners is at a low level.

Table 4: Level of Family Needs Attainment among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	I am able to take proper care of my household meeting all their basic needs through fashion practice	296 (36.1%)	367 (44.7%)	112 (13.6%)	46 (5.6%)	3.112	.682
2.	I have been able to further my education and that of my family members single handedly through my fashion design practice	237 (28.9%)	251 (30.6%)	158 (19.2%)	175 (21.3%)	2.670	.874
3.	I am able to provide my family desires with ease at any given period of time without any form of financial stress	187 (22.8%)	249 (30.3%)	250 (30.5%)	135 (16.4%)	2.594	.916
4.	My family members have never lacked any essential needs as a result of my fashion design practice	193 (23.5%)	218 (26.6%)	262 (31.9%)	148 (18.0%)	2.555	.923
Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.733 (.849); Decision = Moderate Level							

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 showed the level of career success in area of family needs attainment among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics such as means,

standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.733$) clearly indicates that generally, the level of family needs attainment among the graduate fashion design practitioners is at a moderate level.

Table 5: Level of Career Satisfaction among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std.Dev.
1.	I am fulfilled doing fashion design practice	200 (24.4%)	238 (29.0%)	240 (29.2%)	143 (17.4%)	2.603	.904
2.	I have passion for fashion design practice as it is what I have always wanted to do	202 (24.6%)	236 (28.7%)	218 (26.6%)	165 (20.1%)	2.579	.918
3.	My current expectations in fashion design practice is what I wanted to achieve	140 (17.1%)	202 (24.6%)	300 (36.5%)	179 (21.8%)	2.369	.990
4.	I am excited, joyful, happy and have a sense of self-actualization in my fashion design practice	198 (24.1%)	203 (24.7%)	296 (36.1%)	124 (15.1%)	2.579	.918

Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.533 (.933); Decision = Moderate Level

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 5 showed the level of career success in area of career satisfaction among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.533$) clearly indicates that generally, the level of career satisfaction among the graduate fashion design practitioners is at a moderate level.

Research Question Two: What is the availability level of acquired equipment for use among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State?

Table 6: Availability Level of Acquired equipment for Use among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HA	MA	RA	NA	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	Domestic sewing machines such as manual sewing machine, treadle sewing machine, mechanical domestic sewing machine, and electronic domestic sewing machine	238 (29.0%)	301 (36.7%)	254 (30.9%)	28 (3.4%)	2.912	.732

2.	Computerised domestic sewing machine for computerized manner of sewing garments	101 (12.3%)	185 (22.5%)	219 (26.7%)	316 (38.5%)	2.086	1.117
3.	Industrial sewing machines for faster way of sewing clothes	198 (24.1%)	276 (33.6%)	261 (31.8%)	86 (10.5%)	2.714	.781
4.	Stoning machine for stoning garments for customers	134 (16.3%)	182 (22.2%)	237 (28.9%)	268 (32.6%)	2.222	1.110
5.	Weaving/Serger machines or looms for neat finishing of helms and edges of garments	138 (16.8%)	214 (26.1%)	229 (27.9%)	240 (29.2%)	2.305	.999
6.	Embroidery machines for making embroidery on materials	106 (12.9%)	188 (22.9%)	208 (25.3%)	319 (38.9%)	2.099	1.117
7.	Quilting sewing machines for better and more efficient manner of sewing clothes	100 (12.2%)	192 (23.4%)	224 (27.3%)	305 (37.1%)	2.106	1.113
Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.349 (.996); Decision = Rarely Available							

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Key: Highly Available (HA) = 4; Moderately Available (MA) = 3; Rarely Available (RA) = 2; Not Available (NA) = 1; Std. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Threshold Mean: 1.000-1.750 = Not Available; 1.751-2.500 = Rarely Available; 2.501-3.250 = Moderately Available and 3.251 to 4.000 = Highly Available

Table 6 showed the availability level of acquired equipment for use among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The rating scale of Not Available (1) to Highly Available (4) was used. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.349$) clearly and generally indicates rare availability level of acquired equipment for use among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State.

Table 7: Correlation Matrix

Indices	Career Success
Availability level of acquired equipment	Pearson Correlation .138** Sig. (2-tailed) .020 N 821

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 7 showed that availability level of acquired equipment has a positive significant correlation or relationship with career success among graduate fashion design practitioners ($r = .138$; Sig. = .020). This result implies that as availability level of acquired equipment increases, the career success among graduate fashion design practitioners also increases.

Discussion of Findings

This study investigated acquisition of equipment and career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria. Research question one clearly indicates that the level of career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State in areas of acquisition of assets, family needs attainment and career satisfaction is at a moderate level but low level in area of employment generation. The above finding completely disagrees with a work on “entrepreneurial innovativeness and profitability of students’ start-ups” which revealed high profitability (96%) of students’ start-ups profitability or career success in Lagos and Ogun States (Ogbari et al., 2023). Furthermore, the results partially agrees with the work of Adeleke and Ojewale (2023) who established that the level at which youths in Oyo State are developing their career in various business ventures is at a moderate level.

Research question two clearly indicates rare availability level of acquired equipment for use among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State. This finding differs from the result of a study on “modern equipment and tools in clothing applications for entrepreneurship skills development for youth empowerment in Port Harcourt Local Government Area” which revealed that modern equipment such as quilting machines, serger machines and computerized machines for clothing application is moderately available (Azunwena et al., 2018). This finding is in line with a paper on “Challenges Facing Nigerian Fashion Designers Today” which revealed rare availability of infrastructures, facilities and equipments for use among fashion design practitioners (Idoko,2024). The result also agrees completely with that of Iwogbe et al. (2022) who revealed that acquisition of equipment for entrepreneurship in Anambra Metropolis of Anambra State is rarely adequate.

The test of hypothesis one clearly indicates that availability level of acquired equipment has a positive significant correlation or relationship with career success among graduate fashion design practitioners. The result agrees completely with a work which revealed that material resources significantly impact on Entrepreneurship in Anambra Metropolis of Anambra State (Iwogbe et al., 2022). The result is also in line with the work on “influences of creativity and resource availability in the intelligent career framework: empirical investigation of Nigerian Entrepreneurs” which showed a significant contribution of material resource availability on success of Nigerian entrepreneurs such as fashion practitioners (Salisu et al., 2022). The finding is also in line with the result of a study on “modern equipment and tools in clothing applications for entrepreneurship skills development for youth empowerment in Port Harcourt Local Government Area” which revealed that modern equipment such as quilting machines, serger

machines and computerized machines significantly influence youth empowerment (Azunwena et al., 2018).

Conclusion

It can be concluded that the rare availability of acquisition of equipment is responsible for the moderate level of graduate fashion design practitioners' career success in areas of acquisition of assets, family needs attainment, and career satisfaction and low level of career success in area of employment generation in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. The graduate fashion design practitioners should therefore do all they can either by working smarter or harder to ensure that they are able to increase boost their career success.
2. Majority of the graduate fashion design practitioners should try as much as possible to solicit for funds from the government, empowerment organisations, NGOs and useful stakeholders to enable them acquire equipment that can boost their productivity and increase their career success from slightly above low level to a high level.

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